

ZIRCONIUM: ITS ESTIMATION AND SEPARATION. HYDRAZINE SULPHATE

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Hydrazine sulphate precipitates zirconium completely from solutions of p_H 2.8 and above. This reagent also separates the element from Be, Ni and rare earths in the p_H range 2.8 to 3.0 in a single precipitation. Separation from thorium is more delicate and the p_H is critical at 2.8.

During an investigation into the analytical behaviour of zirconium, it has been observed that hydrazine sulphate, while precipitating the element quantitatively from solution of p_H 2.8 and above, provides a method for its separation from certain elements associated with it, particularly thorium and cerite earths.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Estimation of Zirconium.—Two stock solutions of pure zirconyl chloride in 0.1N-HCl were prepared and the zirconium was determined by precipitation with *m*-nitrobenzoic acid and subsequent ignition to ZrO_2 ; 0.0486 g. and 0.0560 g. of ZrO_2 were found in 20 ml. of the two solutions respectively. The same estimations were carried out precipitating with hydrazine sulphate. The zirconium solutions (20 ml.) were first neutralised to Congo red with 0.1N ammonia; 5 drops of 0.1N-HCl were next added and diluted to 350 ml. 5% Hydrazine sulphate solution (50 ml.) was then added. The white precipitate of hydrated zirconia was allowed to settle on a water-bath for about 10 minutes after which it was cooled and filtered, washed first with 0.5% hydrazine sulphate and finally with water and ignited. Experimental values of ZrO_2 found (0.0485 g. and 0.0562 g.) are in excellent agreement with standard values

Separation: (a) From Thorium.—Thorium when present singly is not precipitated until the p_H falls to 4.8. Further hydrazine sulphate appears to exercise an inhibitory influence on the precipitation of thorium by oxalic acid. In an experiment only 0.0750 g. of ThO_2 was found in place of 0.0873 g. taken.

When admixed with zirconium, however, co-precipitation of thorium occurs even at p_H 3.0. Results obtained under varying conditions of p_H are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of p_H on the separation of zirconium from thorium.

		ZrO_2 taken = 0.0486 g. ThO_2 added = 0.876 g.									
Expt. No.	...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
p_H	...	3.4	3.2	3.0	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.2
ZrO_2 (found in g.)		0.0622	0.0568	0.0522	0.0487	0.0485	0.0480	0.0470	0.0449	0.0433	0.0435

Residue corresponding to experiment 1 was fused with sodium bisulphate and the zirconium was estimated with mandelic acid (Kumins, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 376).

ZrO₂ found was 0.0484 g. showing that all the zirconium was precipitated and the excess weight was due to thorium only that was coprecipitated. This was further confirmed by tests on the filtrate for zirconium. The filtrate was concentrated to a small volume by evaporation to 50 ml. H₂SO₄ (10 ml.), 3% H₂O₂ (10 ml.) and sodium hydrogen phosphate failed to show any turbidity which would have been produced in the presence of 0.1 mg. of ZrO₂.

To the mixed solution of zirconium and thorium chlorides 5% hydrazine sulphate (100 ml.) was added and diluted to about 200 ml. The *p_H* was adjusted to 2.8 and kept on a water-bath for 1½ hours. It was then allowed to cool and collected on Whatman No. 42 filter, washed with 0.5% hydrazine sulphate and finally with water. It was ignited and weighed.

(b) *From other Elements.*—Separation from other elements, viz. Be, Ni and rare earths is more simple. The procedure outlined for the determination of zirconium was employed. Iron was reduced and the precipitation of zirconium was not complete. In the presence of aluminium some zirconium was held in solution. Uranium, tin, and titanium were precipitated along with zirconium. Results obtained are given in Table II.

TABLE II

	ZrO ₂ (taken).	Elements added.	ZrO ₂ (found).	Difference.
1.	0.0486 g.	R ₂ O ₃ 0.2004 g	0.0486 g.	0.0000 g.
2.	—	— 0.4008	0.0485	-0.0001
3.	—	Ni 0.4012	0.0488	+0.0002
4.	—	BeO 0.3786	0.0485	-0.0001
5.	—	ThO ₂ 0.0876	0.0488	+0.0002
6.	—	— 0.1752	0.0486	-0.0000
7.	0.0562	— 0.0876	0.0562	0.0000
8.	—	— 0.1752	0.0564	+0.0002

CONCLUSION

Hydrazine sulphate precipitates zirconium quantitatively in solutions of *p_H* 2.8 and higher. Separation from thorium in a single precipitation is effective at *p_H* 2.8. This is rather critical. Separation from Be, Ni and rare earths can be accomplished over a wider *p_H* range, 2.8 to 3.0.